

The Chemistry of Furan Derivatives : The Hydride Reduction of Furfurylidene N-Aryl Amines

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In the past few years, the chemistry of furan ring system and its derivatives has attracted much attention¹. The ring is attacked both by electrophiles and nucleophiles and sometimes this accompanies with opening of the ring. This is obviously due to the less aromatic character of the furan ring as compared with other heterocycles. The formation of imine derivatives from furfural and aromatic amines have been the subject of controversy² and recently ring opening of furan in methanol has been described. In this investigation the smooth preparation of furfurylidene arylamines is described and they have been further converted to furfurylamines with sodium borohydride without effecting the furan ring.

The furfurylidene arylamines I were prepared by mixing equimolar quantities of freshly distilled furfural and the corresponding amine at room temperature in methanol. The imines were precipitated by diluting with ice-cold water and were characterised.

The azomethine structure I assigned to these compounds is supported by elemental analysis i.r., n.m.r., and mass spectrum. The i.r. spectrum (in Nujol, Infracord) of I showed absorptions at 1625 cm^{-1} assignable to $\text{CH}=\text{N}$ bond. In n.m.r. spectrum (60 MHz, in CDCl_3) the azomethine proton was indicated at 1.7τ and the aromatic protons in the region $2.7\text{--}3.1\tau$ (8H) multiplet. The characteristics of these imines are recorded in Table-1. The sodium borohydride reduction was carried out at 0°C in methanol. The sodium borohydride powder was added slowly to a solution of imine in methanol. After the completion of the reaction, reaction mixture was refluxed on water bath to destroy the excess sodium borohydride. The dihydro products were obtained on extraction with ether and ether was then evaporated. These products were recrystallized from petroleum-ether. The elemental analysis and molecular weight determination indicated the compound to be II. The i.r. spectrum indicated—NH at $3380\text{--}\text{cm}^{-1}$ and gave no absorption above 1600 cm^{-1} . The characteristics of these dihydro products are recorded in Table-1.

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1. P. Bosshard and C. H. Eusster, *Advances in Hetero-cyclic chemistry*, Academic Press, N.Y., Volume VII, 1968, p. 378-478.
2. K. G. Lewis and C. E. Mulquiney, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1968, 1249.

TABLE I

Sr. No.	X	m.p. °C	I.R. absorption of CH=N	Mol. Wt. M _f *	Yield % and solvent of crystallisation	Imines I		Analysis N%		m.p. °C	Yield %	Dihydro products II	
						CH=N	Yield % and solvent of crystallisation	Calcd.	Found			Calcd.	Found
1.	H	58	1625 cm ⁻¹	171	90 Petroleum ether	8.17	8.01	(147°/10 mm)*	90	C = 76.30 H = 6.63 N = 8.09	76.21 6.58 7.995		
2.	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	76	1620 cm ⁻¹	215	95 benzene-hexane	6.51	6.43	62	85	C = 71.88 H = 6.91 N = 6.43	71.62 6.86 6.39		
3.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	69	1620 cm ⁻¹	201	85 petroleum ether	6.97	6.81	46	90	C = 71.64 H = 6.46 N = 6.86	71.49 6.40 6.78		
4.	<i>p</i> -Cl	51-2	1625 cm ⁻¹	205.5	90 benzene-petroleum ether	6.82	6.70	30-31	95	C = 64.23 H = 9.86 N = 6.74 Cl = 17.27	64.15 9.79 6.68 17.17		
5.	<i>p</i> -Br	62-3	1625 cm ⁻¹	250	hexane	5.60	5.52	50-51	98	C = 52.80 H = 4.00 N = 5.55 Br = 32.00	52.72 3.92 5.48 31.88		

* The M⁺ was determined through Mass spectral analysis. Elemental analysis was obtained through Australian Micro Analytical Services CSIRO (Australia).

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